

MEDICAL SCIENCES

ORTHODONTIC TREATMENT TECHNOLOGIES FOR PATIENTS WITH CLEFT LIP AND PALATE

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Abstract

A search and analysis of literature sources related to the results of clinical studies on orthodontic treatment of children with cleft lip and palate was conducted. Modern methods of diagnosis and treatment of this pathology were reviewed.

Keywords: orthodontic treatment, cleft lip, cleft palate.

Relevance of the Topic

Cleft lip and palate are considered among the most common congenital anomalies in humans [1]. This pathology occurs in approximately 1 in 700 newborns [2], with its incidence varying depending on race, ethnic and geographic region, the child's sex, and the family's socioeconomic status. Unfortunately, there is currently a trend toward an increasing number of newborns diagnosed with this condition.

Such a defect can lead to significant negative consequences for affected individuals, including difficulties with feeding during infancy, impaired physical development, delayed or improper development of hearing and speech, disharmonious facial growth and occlusion, as well as psychological and emotional challenges [2].

Treatment for children with cleft lip and palate is long-term, beginning at birth and continuing until the age of 16–18 years. Primary surgical interventions are typically performed shortly after birth, usually within the first year of life, and aim to restore both aesthetics and function. However, these early surgeries may adversely affect the future growth and development of the maxilla [3, 4, 5, 6].

Orthodontic Treatment

Orthodontic treatment is one of the key components in the multidisciplinary rehabilitation of patients with cleft lip and palate. The need for specialized orthodontic care is increasing, leading to a growing number of research methods. Selecting diagnostic tools that are both clinically valuable and meaningful for practitioners and patients is becoming increasingly important.

Patients who underwent surgery in childhood often present with skeletal Class III malocclusion, a concave facial profile, posterior crossbite, transverse maxillary constriction, and misalignment of teeth adjacent to the cleft defect [3]. Anomalies in the number, shape, and position of individual teeth are frequently observed [3, 4, 5, 6]. The absence of the lateral incisor on the cleft

side of the maxilla is the most common dental anomaly in unilateral cleft lip and palate cases [7, 8, 9].

Diagnostic models are an essential part of treatment planning, monitoring, and achieving successful outcomes. They are also used in the fabrication of orthodontic appliances, and their accuracy directly affects the quality of appliance construction and the final treatment result.

The challenges associated with the production, storage, and transportation of plaster models have led to the development of virtual 3D jaw models [10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15]. Comparative studies between plaster and 3D models have demonstrated the clear advantages of the latter. Thus, 3D dental arch analysis is currently the most advanced diagnostic method, enabling an effective assessment of the clinical situation [11, 12, 15].

Cephalometric Analysis

Evidence-based medicine and clinical observations indicate the negative impact of orofacial anomalies on dentofacial growth. These changes are caused by the consequences of cleft lip and palate, as well as by surgical interventions, including scarring after operations [16].

Cephalometric analysis is a fundamental diagnostic tool used to establish a diagnosis and select an appropriate treatment method. This method provides clinicians with essential data and information needed to predict treatment outcomes.

Cephalometric analysis can be performed on both 2D lateral skull radiographs and using computed tomography (CT). The results obtained through CT are more accurate and informative. Today, when choosing a method for diagnosing bone structures, the majority of researchers and clinicians prefer CT.

Diagnosis of the Upper Airways

It is known that children with cleft palate and lip exhibit distinct developmental features of the facial skeleton compared to patients with other dentofacial anomalies. These differences include shortening and narrowing of the maxilla, its retruded position relative

to the cranial base [17, 18, 19, 20], counterclockwise rotation of the mandible, an increase in the gonial angle [17, 18, 19], and retrusion of the upper central incisors [20].

According to the literature, the volume of the upper airways depends on the sagittal and vertical dimensions of skeletal structures [21, 22, 23], retrusion and underdevelopment of the maxilla or mandible, and backward rotation of the mandible. All these factors contribute to the narrowing of the airways and impaired respiratory function [24].

Changes in the volume of the upper airways are not age-dependent [25], but they significantly affect a child's physical and psychosomatic development.

Electromyographic Studies of Muscles

Swallowing and chewing functions are often altered in patients with cleft lip and palate [26]. A short upper lip is a characteristic clinical sign in such patients. Scar tissue that forms in the upper lip area after surgical intervention can inhibit the development of the maxilla [27]. Restoring the function of the upper lip is therefore a crucial component of comprehensive treatment for these patients.

Maintaining myodynamic balance between antagonist and synergist muscles creates favorable conditions for the normal development of the dentofacial system. Disruption of masticatory function due to uncoordinated activity of these muscles is a significant etiological factor in the development of malocclusions and misalignment of individual teeth.

Electromyography is one of the few diagnostic tools that allows for an objective assessment of muscle function [28].

Orthodontic Treatment of Children and Adolescents with Cleft Lip and Palate

Patients with cleft lip and palate typically present with Angle Class III occlusion, maxillary constriction and shortening, and anomalies in the size and position of individual teeth. Therefore, the primary task of the orthodontist—especially during the mixed dentition period—is to expand the maxilla and prepare for subsequent surgical interventions.

To achieve this, various orthodontic appliances are used, with the choice depending on the specific clinical situation. According to the literature, the **Hyrax** and **Quad Helix** appliances are the most common and effective devices in these cases, typically used with a slow activation protocol [1, 3]. The effectiveness of treatment is influenced more by the patient's dental age than their chronological age [3].

Maxillary expansion is achieved by widening the midpalatal suture, resulting in lateral displacement of the alveolar segments [29, 30], and is considered effective and complete once the posterior crossbite has been corrected [10].

In patients with cleft of the hard palate, expansion does not lead to bone formation due to the absence of the palatal suture. Therefore, the expansion appliance must remain in place as a retention device until surgical intervention is performed.

Patients and their families should be informed about the necessity of continued orthodontic treatment—whether combined with surgery or not.

Conclusion

The treatment of cleft lip and palate is a complex task that requires a coordinated effort from a multidisciplinary medical team. The primary goals of treatment are to restore function and aesthetics, improve the patient's quality of life, and enhance self-esteem.

Effective treatment planning relies on comprehensive diagnostic methods, including anthropometric measurements on plaster and 3D jaw models, cephalometric analysis, assessment of masticatory muscle function, and evaluation of upper airway volume.

These diagnostic tools provide essential data for creating individualized treatment plans and contribute to the development of evidence-based multidisciplinary treatment protocols for children and adolescents with cleft lip and palate.

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